

SOMEWHAT PAIRWISE FUZZY e -IRRESOLUTE MAPPINGS

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ABSTRACT. The concepts of somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mapping and somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open mapping is introduced. Also some properties and comparisons of those mappings are given.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concepts of fuzzy sets introduced by Zadeh[7]. Chang [2] studied the notion of fuzzy topology in 1968. Seenivasan and Kamala [3] introduced the concept of fuzzy e -continuous functions in fuzzy topological spaces. The concepts of somewhat fuzzy e -continuous functions and somewhat fuzzy e -open functions are introduced and studied by Swaminathan in [6]. The purpose of this paper is to introduce and study the concepts of somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mappings and somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open mappings on a fuzzy bitopological spaces and also we discuss some of their properties.

A fuzzy subset A of a space X is called fuzzy regular open [1] (resp. fuzzy regular closed) if $A = \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(A))$ (resp. $A = \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A))$). Now $\text{Cl}(A)$ and $\text{Int}(A)$ are defined as follows: $\text{Cl}(A) = \bigwedge \{U : U \geq A, U \text{ is fuzzy closed in } X\}$ and $\text{Int}(A) = \bigvee \{U \leq A, U \text{ is fuzzy open in } X\}$. The fuzzy δ -interior of a fuzzy subset A of X is the union of all fuzzy regular open sets contained in A . A fuzzy subset A is called fuzzy δ -open [4] if $A = \text{Int}_\delta(A)$. The complement of fuzzy δ -open set is called fuzzy δ -closed (i.e, $A = \text{Cl}_\delta(A)$).

A fuzzy subset A of a space X is called fuzzy e -open[3] if $A \leq \text{cl}(\text{int}_\delta A) \vee \text{int}(\text{cl}_\delta A)$ and fuzzy e -closed set if $A \geq \text{cl}(\text{int}_\delta A) \wedge \text{int}(\text{cl}_\delta A)$. Throughout this paper X and Y stand for $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ and $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ respectively.

Definition 1.1. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called fuzzy e -continuous [3] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is a fuzzy e -open set on X for any fuzzy open set V on Y .

Definition 1.2. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called somewhat fuzzy e -continuous[6] if there exists a fuzzy e -open set $U \neq 0_X$ on X such that $U \leq f^{-1}(V) \neq 0_X$ for any fuzzy open set V on Y .

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Definition 1.3. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called somewhat fuzzy e -open[6] if there exists a fuzzy e -open set $V \neq 0_Y$ on Y such that $V \leq f(U) \neq 0_Y$ for any fuzzy open set U on X .

Definition 1.4. A fuzzy set U on a fuzzy topological space X is called fuzzy e -dense[6] if there exists no fuzzy e -closed set V in X such that $U < V < 1$.

2. SOMEWHAT PAIRWISE FUZZY e -IRRESOLUTE MAPPINGS

In this section we introduce a somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mapping and compared few results.

Definition 2.1. A mapping $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ is called pairwise fuzzy e -continuous if $f^{-1}(V)$ is a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ for any \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy open set V on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$.

Definition 2.2. A mapping $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ is called pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute if $f^{-1}(V)$ is a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ for any \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set V on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$.

Definition 2.3. A mapping $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ is called somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -continuous if there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $U \neq 0_X$ on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $U \leq f^{-1}(V) \neq 0_X$ for any \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy open set $V \neq 0_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$.

Definition 2.4. A mapping $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ is called somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute if there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $U \neq 0_X$ on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $U \leq f^{-1}(V) \neq 0_X$ for any \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $V \neq 0_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$.

Remark. From the above definitions, it is observed that the following reverse implications are false:

- (i) Every pairwise fuzzy e -continuous mapping is a somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -continuous mapping.
- (ii) Every somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mapping is a somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -continuous mapping.
- (iii) Every pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mapping is a somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mapping.

Example 2.5. Let M_1, M_2, M_3, M_4 and M_5 be fuzzy sets on $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$. Then $M_1 = \frac{0.3}{a} + \frac{0.4}{b} + \frac{0.5}{c}$, $M_2 = \frac{0.6}{a} + \frac{0.5}{b} + \frac{0.5}{c}$, $M_3 = \frac{0.7}{a} + \frac{0.6}{b} + \frac{0.4}{c}$, $M_4 = \frac{0.3}{x} + \frac{0.4}{y} + \frac{0.4}{z}$ and $M_5 = \frac{0.6}{x} + \frac{0.5}{y} + \frac{0.4}{z}$ are defined as follows: Consider $\mathcal{T}_1 = \{0_X, M_1, M_2, M_4, M_5, 1_X\}$, $\mathcal{T}_2 = \{0_X, M_1, M_2, M_4, 1_X\}$, $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{0_X, M_1, M_1^c, M_2, M_3, M_4, M_5, 1_X\}$ and $\mathcal{F}_2 = \{0_X, M_1, M_5, 1_X\}$. Then $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ and $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ are fuzzy bitopologies and $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ be an identity mapping. Then we have $M_1 \leq f^{-1}(M_1) = M_1$, $M_1 \leq f^{-1}(M_1^c) = M_1^c$, $M_1 \leq f^{-1}(M_2) = M_2$, $M_4 \leq f^{-1}(M_3) = M_3$, $M_4 \leq f^{-1}(M_4) = M_4$ and $M_4 \leq f^{-1}(M_5) = M_5$. Since M_1, M_2 and M_4 are \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$, f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -continuous. But $f^{-1}(M_3) = M_3$ is not a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$. Hence f is not a pairwise fuzzy e -continuous mapping.

Example 2.6. Let $\mu_1(x)$, $\mu_2(x)$ and $\mu_3(x)$ be fuzzy sets on $I = [0, 1]$ defined as follows:

$$\mu_1(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ 2x - 1, & \frac{1}{2} \leq x \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\mu_2(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & 0 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ -4x + 2, & \frac{1}{2} \leq x \leq \frac{3}{4} \\ 0, & \frac{3}{4} \leq x \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\mu_3(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{4} \\ \frac{1}{3}(4x - 1), & \frac{1}{4} \leq x \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

Let $\mathcal{T}_1 = \{0, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_1 \vee \mu_2, 1\}$ and $\mathcal{T}_2 = \{0, \mu_1 \vee \mu_2, 1\}$, $\mathcal{T}_3 = \{0, \mu'_2, 1\}$ and $\mathcal{T}_4 = \{0, \mu'_1, 1\}$ be a fuzzy topologies on I . Let $f : (I, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (I, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ be a function defined by $f(x) = \frac{x}{2}$ for each $x \in I$. We can see that for fuzzy e -open sets μ'_1 and μ'_2 on $(I, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$, $f^{-1}(\mu'_1) = 1_X, \mu_1 \leq f^{-1}(\mu'_2) = \mu_1$. Since μ_1 is a fuzzy e -open set on $(I, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$. Therefore f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -continuous mapping. Consider a fuzzy open set μ_3 which is fuzzy e -open set on $(I, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$, $f^{-1}(\mu_3) = \mu_3 f(\frac{x}{2}) = \alpha(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{3}(2x - 1), & \frac{1}{2} \leq x \leq 1 \end{cases}$ for each $x \in I$. But there is no non-zero fuzzy e -open set smaller than $f^{-1}(\mu_3(x)) = \alpha(x)$ on $(I, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$. Hence f is not somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mapping.

Example 2.7. In Example 2.5, for an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open sets on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$, $M_4 \leq f^{-1}(M_1) = M_1$, $M_4 \leq f^{-1}(M_1^c) = M_1^c, M_4 \leq f^{-1}(M_2) = M_2, M_4 \leq f^{-1}(M_3) = M_3, M_4 \leq f^{-1}(M_4) = M_4$ and $M_4 \leq f^{-1}(M_5) = M_5$. Since M_4 is a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$, f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -continuous. But $f^{-1}(M_3) = M_3$ is not a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$. Hence f is not a pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mapping.

Definition 2.8. A fuzzy set U on a fuzzy bitopological space $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ is called pairwise e -dense fuzzy set if there exists no \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set V in $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $U < V < 1$.

Theorem 2.1. Let $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ be a mapping. Then the following are equivalent:

- (1) f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute.
- (2) If V is an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set of $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $f^{-1}(V) \neq 1_X$, then there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set $U \neq 1_X$ of $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $f^{-1}(V) \leq U$.
- (3) If U is a pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$, then $f(U)$ is a pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$.

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2): Let V be an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $f^{-1}(V) \neq 1_X$. Then V^c is an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ and $f^{-1}(V^c) = (f^{-1}(V))^c \neq 0_X$. Since f is somewhat pairwise e -irresolute, there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $U^c \neq 0_X$ on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $U^c \leq f^{-1}(V^c)$. Hence there exists \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set $U \neq 0_X$ on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $f^{-1}(V) = 1 - f^{-1}(V^c) \leq 1 - U^c = U$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3): Let U be a pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ and suppose $f(U)$ is not pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$. Then there exists an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set V on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $f(U) < V < 1$. Since $V < 1$ and $f^{-1}(V) \neq 1_X$, there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set $D \neq 1_X$ such that $U \leq f^{-1}(f(U)) < f^{-1}(V) \leq D$. This contradicts to the assumption that U is a

pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$. Hence $f(U)$ is a pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$.

(3) \Rightarrow (1): Let $V \neq 0_Y$ be an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ and let $f^{-1}(V) \neq 0_X$. Suppose that there exists no \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $U \neq 0_X$ on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $U \leq f^{-1}(V)$. Then $(f^{-1}(V))^c$ is a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy set or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that there is no \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set D on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ with $(f^{-1}(V))^c < D < 1$. In fact, if there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set D^c such that $D^c \leq f^{-1}(V)$, then it is a contradiction. So $(f^{-1}(V))^c$ is a pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$. Then $f((f^{-1}(V))^c)$ is a pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$. But $f((f^{-1}(V))^c) = f(f^{-1}(V^c)) \neq V^c < 1$. This is a contradiction to the fact that $f((f^{-1}(V))^c)$ is pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$. Hence there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $U \neq 0_X$ on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $U \leq f^{-1}(V)$. Consequently, f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute. \square

Theorem 2.2. Let $(X_1, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2), (X_2, \mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2), (Y_1, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2), (Y_2, \mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2)$ be fuzzy bitopological spaces. Let $(X_1, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ be product related to $(X_2, \mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2)$ and let $(Y_1, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ be product related to $(Y_2, \mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2)$. If $f_1 : (X_1, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y_1, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ and $f_2 : (X_2, \mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2) \rightarrow (Y_2, \mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2)$ is a somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mappings, then the product $f_1 \times f_2 : (X_1, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \times (X_2, \mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2) \rightarrow (Y_1, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2) \times (Y_2, \mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2)$ is also somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute.

Proof. Let $C = \bigvee_{i,j} (U_i \times V_j)$ be \mathcal{F}_i -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{K}_j -fuzzy e -open set on $(Y_1, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2) \times (Y_2, \mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2)$ where $U_i \neq 0_{Y_1}$ is \mathcal{F}_i -fuzzy e -open set and $V_j \neq 0_{Y_2}$ is \mathcal{K}_j -fuzzy e -open set on $(Y_1, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ and $(Y_2, \mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2)$ respectively. Then $(f_1 \times f_2)^{-1}(C) = \bigvee_{i,j} (f_1^{-1}(U_i) \times f_2^{-1}(V_j))$. Since f_1 is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute, there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $D_i \neq 0_{X_1}$ such that $D_i \leq f_1^{-1}(U_i) \neq 0_{X_1}$. And, since f_2 is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute, there exists a \mathcal{G}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{G}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $A_j \neq 0_{X_2}$ such that $A_j \leq f_2^{-1}(V_j) \neq 0_{X_2}$. Now $D_i \times A_j \leq f_1^{-1}(U_i) \times f_2^{-1}(V_j) = (f_1 \times f_2)^{-1}(U_i \times V_j)$ and $D_i \times A_j \neq 0_{X_1 \times X_2}$ is a D_i -fuzzy e -open or V_j -fuzzy e -open set on $(X_1, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \times (X_2, \mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2)$. Hence $D_i \times A_j$ is a \mathcal{T}_i -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{G}_j -fuzzy e -open set on $(X_1, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \times (X_2, \mathcal{G}_1, \mathcal{G}_2)$ such that $\bigvee_{i,j} (D_i \times A_j) \leq \bigvee_{i,j} (f_1^{-1}(U_i) \times f_2^{-1}(V_j)) = (f_1 \times f_2)^{-1}(\bigvee_{i,j} (U_i \times V_j)) = (f_1 \times f_2)^{-1}(C) \neq 0_{X_1 \times X_2}$. Therefore, $f_1 \times f_2$ is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute. \square

Theorem 2.3. Let $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ be a mapping. If the graph $g : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \times (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ of f is a somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mapping, then f is also somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute.

Proof. Let V be an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$. Then $f^{-1}(V) = 1 \wedge f^{-1}(V) = g^{-1}(1 \times V)$. Since g is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute and $1 \times V$ is a \mathcal{T}_i -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_j -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \times (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$, there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $U \neq 0_X$ on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $U \leq g^{-1}(1 \times V) = f^{-1}(V) \neq 0_X$. Therefore, f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute. \square

3. SOMEWHAT PAIRWISE FUZZY IRRESOLUTE e -OPEN MAPPINGS

In this section, we introduce a somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open mapping and we characterize a somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open mapping.

Definition 3.1. A mapping $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ is called pairwise fuzzy e -open if $f(U)$ is an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ for any \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy open set U on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$.

Definition 3.2. A mapping $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ is called pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open if $f(U)$ is an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ for any \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set U on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$.

Definition 3.3. A mapping $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ is called somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -open if there exists an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $V \neq 0_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $V \leq f(U) \neq 0_Y$ for any \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy open set U on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$.

Definition 3.4. A mapping $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ is called somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open if there exists an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $V \neq 0_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $V \leq f(U) \neq 0_Y$ for any \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $U \neq 0_X$ on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$.

Theorem 3.1. Let $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ be a bijection. Then the following are equivalent:

- (1) f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open.
- (2) If U is a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $f(U) \neq 1_Y$, then there exists an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set $V \neq 1_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $f(U) < V$.

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2): Let U be a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $f(U) \neq 1_Y$. Since f is bijective and U^c is a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$, $f(U^c) = (f(U))^c \neq 0_Y$. And, since f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open mapping, there exists an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $D \neq 0_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $D < f(U^c) = (f(U))^c$. Consequently, $f(U) < D^c = V \neq 1_Y$ and V is an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1): Let U be a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $f(U) \neq 0_Y$. Then U^c is a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ and $f(U^c) \neq 1_Y$. Hence there exists an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set $V \neq 1_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $f(U^c) < V$. Since f is bijective, $f(U^c) = (f(U))^c < V$. Hence $V^c < f(U)$ and $V^c \neq 0_X$ is an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$. Therefore, f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open. □

Theorem 3.2. Let $f : (X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2) \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ be a surjection. Then the following are equivalent:

- (1) f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open.
- (2) If V is a pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$, then $f^{-1}(V)$ is a pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$.

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2): Let V be a pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$. Suppose $f^{-1}(V)$ is not pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$. Then there exists a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set U on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ such that $f^{-1}(V) < U < 1$. Since f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open and U^c is a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy e -open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$, there exists an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $D \neq 0_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $D \leq f(IntU^c) \leq f(U^c)$. Since f is surjective, $D \leq f(U^c) < f(f^{-1}(V^c)) = V^c$. Thus there exists an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set D^c

on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $V < D^c < 1$. This is a contradiction. Hence $f^{-1}(V)$ is pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1): Let U be a \mathcal{T}_1 -fuzzy open or \mathcal{T}_2 -fuzzy open set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$ and $f(U) \neq 0_Y$. Suppose there exists no \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $V \neq 0_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $V \leq f(U)$. Then $(f(U))^c$ is an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy set or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy set D on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that there exists no \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -closed or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -closed set D on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ with $(f(U))^c < D < 1$. This means that $(f(U))^c$ is pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$. Thus $f^{-1}((f(U))^c)$ is pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$. But $f^{-1}((f(U))^c) = (f^{-1}(f(U)))^c \leq U^c < 1$. This is a contradiction to the fact that $f^{-1}(f(U))^c$ is pairwise e -dense fuzzy set on $(X, \mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2)$. Hence there exists an \mathcal{F}_1 -fuzzy e -open or \mathcal{F}_2 -fuzzy e -open set $V \neq 0_Y$ on $(Y, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2)$ such that $V \leq f(U)$. Therefore, f is somewhat pairwise fuzzy irresolute e -open. \square

4. CONCLUSIONS AND/OR DISCUSSIONS

Even though the concept of somewhat fuzzy continuous functions are not at all fuzzy continuous functions, it has some interesting stuff to develop further. In this aspect the somewhat fuzzy δ -irresolute continuous and somewhat fuzzy e -irresolute continuous mappings were investigated in [5] and [6] respectively. From these papers, we have developed and studied this research article in fuzzy bitopology as somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute mappings; this paper only concerned with somewhat pairwise fuzzy e -irresolute functions with some interesting properties.

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